

The logo for WYRED is presented within two overlapping speech bubbles. The top bubble is blue and contains the letters 'WY', while the bottom bubble is orange and contains the letters 'RED'. The background of the entire page is a photograph of young people in a classroom or workshop, looking at a laptop screen. The image has a blue color cast in the upper portion and an orange color cast in the lower portion.

WYRED

NETWORKED YOUTH RESEARCH
FOR EMPOWERMENT IN THE
DIGITAL SOCIETY

MANIFESTO

TO THE OLDER GENERATIONS

We, young people, living in this digital society, want to feel that our voices matter. But the people with power don't listen to us.

We want to be heard always, not only when you need us.

We want to define the burning issues for ourselves. We want to decide, for ourselves, on how we will discuss them and what kind of digital society we want to live in.

We want to build a network of peers around the world, with all our differences, to raise our voices and create safe spaces to express ourselves, share and create. Spaces in which we can explore our interests in this digital society.

We also need a platform from which we can communicate with the people who decide things in our society. We want them to be in touch with us directly and listen to what we have to say.

WE WANT:

TO BE HEARD: Don't listen to us only when you need us. Join our spaces, take part in discussions, listen to what we have to say. Decision makers need to be available and open for our opinions.

TO BE SAFE: We want to feel and be safe, live without fake news and hate speech. Internet is not a place for hate and lies but for keeping us connected, informed and human. We don't want to be afraid when online.

TO KNOW, BE INFORMED AND AWARE: Make the rules of internet understandable and clear. We want to know what data is being collected about us. We want the internet to be free and neutral. We want to exercise our right to be able to remove and be deliberately forgotten.

TO HAVE DIGNITY AND RESPECT: Digital society needs to be respectful, inclusive and non-violent. We want human connections, friends and not bullies.

TO HAVE ACCESS: All generations need to be supported to be online and internet needs to be accessible and free for everyone. And everyone needs to understand what they see online, so we want digital education to be improved

IN WYRED WE WANT TO
MAKE OUR VOICES LOUDER
EXPLORE THE THINGS THAT MATTER
UNDERSTAND OUR DIGITAL WORLD BETTER
AND
TELL THE PEOPLE IN POWER

Note:

The WYRED Manifesto has been created based on consultations with young people in different face to face meetings and events, Delphi2 research and the WYRED platform. At least 300 young people from all over Europe, between 15-30 years of age, took part in its creation and formulation. The manifesto will continue to be a consultative document throughout WYRED project. This document is a collection of young people's thoughts.

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